

FOOD SECURITY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotation. Today, environmental and other problems such as drought, desertification and water scarcity threaten food security throughout the planet. The article focuses on the essence of the concept of food safety and the main directions of state policy to ensure it.

Key words: food security, United Nations Food and Agriculture Agency (FAO), per capita daily energy consumption (DEC), food balance, global hunger index (GHI).

The food supply of the population depends on the food security of the country. Because the volume of production of food products at the national level should ensure the country's need for it without depending on external factors (foreign countries). As a result, political-economic and social stability is ensured at the country level.

The President of our republic, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has been promoting advanced initiatives on global problems and their solutions at various international forums and summits. In particular, the issue of food security is a priority among the initiatives of the head of state. This shows that the issue of food safety is in the center of attention even at the national level.

Such initiatives and proposals of the head of our state to ensure food safety are important in eliminating the problems and obstacles in this field and mitigating threats to food safety, which are becoming more and more serious.

In a word, environmental and other problems such as drought, desertification, water scarcity, and other problems, in turn, threaten food security all over the planet. Continuous attention to food problems and long-term programs and plans in this direction, and cooperative efforts are crucial.

The concept of food security was first proposed at the World Food Summit in 1974, and refers to "the availability at all times of sufficient global reserves of staple foods to ensure sustained growth in food consumption and to cover fluctuations in production and prices" [1].

Measures taken to achieve food security in different countries can be divided into four groups: production support, trade, consumption and micronutrient supply.

In recent years, the concept of food safety has expanded to include the safety and nutritional value of food products, as well as personal preferences.

In 2001, in addition to physical and economic opportunity, the concept of social opportunity was added to the concept of food security.

The current Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) definition reflects this additional dimension as follows: "all people have access to sufficient safe and nutritious food to meet their nutritional needs and personal preferences and to lead an active and healthy life." Having physical, economic and social opportunities to be food security is ensured.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the share of the world's population suffering from insufficient nutrition is 8.9% in 2019 and more than 690 million people. Every year in developing countries, 20 million children are born underweight, malnutrition causes the death of 5 million children, and those who survive suffer from various diseases.

According to FAO experts, the situation in terms of food security is determined by indicators of food security, the possibility of obtaining stability of supply and health. They are defined in detail below:

- **Stability:** a population, family or individual must always have access to food so that the food supply is not interrupted. They should not be cut off from food due to unexpected events (eg economic or climate crisis) or cyclical events (eg climate food shortages).

- **Food availability:** supply of the necessary quality food products in the required quantity through domestic production or importation (including food aid). The most commonly used measure of food availability is per capita daily energy expenditure (DEE), measured in calories. According to the FAO methods, the KES indicator is calculated according to the type of food consumption based on the food balance. FAO calculates food balances using information on different sources of food supply (production, savings, trade) and different uses (or consumption) of products (forage, seed, industrial use, waste) of specific commodities.

- **Access to food:** the physical, economic and social capacity to access the necessary resources in order to obtain the nutrients necessary for a nutritious diet. Physical food supply implies that food products are available in the market in the quantity and choice demanded by consumers, and that there is an infrastructure for providing food products to the population. Economic opportunity means that all social strata of the population can afford to buy enough food products. In other words, economic opportunity means that households have enough income to buy food and the country has enough foreign exchange to import food. Social opportunity means that the entire population, regardless of culture or religion, is fairly provided with food.

- **Utilization:** achieving a state in which all physiological needs are met with food consumption through adequate nutrition, clean water, sanitation and health care.

Failure to meet an indicator results in low food security or food insecurity. Food insecurity is a situation in which people do not get enough safe and nutritious food for growth, development, and an active lifestyle. Food insecurity or low levels of food security lead to poor nutrition among the population, which in turn has serious consequences for individuals, families and the nation as a whole.

Therefore, the national policy of food security is developed and implemented according to the above four components of food security. Since the first years of independence, food safety issues have been in one of the central places in the socio-economic policy of Uzbekistan.

Now, the issues of further improving the welfare and quality of life of the population, providing the population with food are closely related to the problem of ensuring food safety.

Agriculture plays an important role in ensuring food security. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, in his speech at the joint meeting of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, said, "The issues of agricultural reform and ensuring food security, without a doubt, remain one of the most important tasks for us. First of all, a lot of attention is paid to the consistent development of the agro-industrial complex and its locomotive, i.e. multi-branch farms, which are the driving force"[2]. stated that.

Sustainable development of agriculture and food chain of the Republic of Uzbekistan requires conducting state policy on the basis of new approaches. The strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030, adopted in this regard, serves to implement these tasks.

The main goal of this Strategy is to fundamentally improve the state policy while deepening the reforms aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the agricultural and food industry. In the strategy, as of 2018, the share of undernourished people in Uzbekistan is 6.3 percent. It is planned to reduce this share to 5 percent by 2021, to 3 percent by 2025, and to zero by 2030. At the same time, the strategy covers the following priority areas:

ensuring food security of the population;

creating a favorable agribusiness environment and value chain;

reducing state participation in industry management and increasing investment attractiveness;

ensuring rational use of natural resources and environmental protection;

development of modern systems of state administration;

gradual diversification of government expenditures aimed at supporting the network;

development of the system of science, education, information and consulting services in agriculture;

development of rural areas;

development of a transparent system of network statistics.

Food security depends on a wide range of socio-economic, demographic and environmental factors and is one of the main components of the country's development.

The implementation of measures defined in this strategy made it possible to develop agriculture at a rapid pace. In particular, during the last 20 years, the area of agricultural crops decreased by 13.7%, in 2019, 216.3 trillion soums, 250.3 trillion soums in 2020, and 303 trillion soums were produced in 2021.

In recent years, as a result of the implementation of a number of measures to strengthen food safety in our country, Uzbekistan has managed to strengthen its position in the world and has gradually improved its position in global rankings. In particular, as we know, every year the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) announces the ranking of the best countries in the Global Hunger Index, which is one of the most important indices representing the food security of countries.

This index is determined by summing four indicators for each country:

- the share of the population that is undernourished;
- the percentage of underweight children under the age of five;
- the share of children under the age of five;
- the mortality rate of children under five years of age.

According to this indicator, the Republic of Uzbekistan took 52nd place among 119 countries in 2018 and reached the "moderate" level with 12.1 points, in 2019 it took 48th place with 10.7 points, and in 2020 it took 30th place among 107 countries with 6.7 points. and in 2021 it took 21st place among 116 countries with 5.9 points.

At the same time, achieving the stability of food supply for the population in need of social protection, increasing the purchasing power of low-income families, and preventing sharp changes in the price and quantity of products are among the problems that need to be solved today.

Therefore, the main goal of this priority is to develop a state policy aimed at ensuring the food security of all the population of the republic and its effective implementation.

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